

Ontologies and controlled vocabularies support in Dataverse

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[Ontologies and controlled vocabularies support in Dataverse](#)

[Current State:](#)

[Consensus Proposal \(draft/being edited\)](#)

[Benefits](#)

[Limitations](#)

[Required Development](#)

[Controlled Vocabulary Value Support Frequently Asked Questions List](#)

[Earlier Discussion](#)

[Requirements/Desired Functionality:](#)

[Discussion/Considerations:](#)

[Current Options/Analysis:](#)

[Design\(s\)](#)

[Requirements Matrix](#)

[SKOSMOS deployments](#)

Current State:

Dataverse supports use of internally managed controlled vocabularies as part of metadata blocks. Any metadata block field can be associated with a fixed list of terms that are the allowed values for that field. The user interface for entering values supports picking from a drop-down list of all available values. The display interface simply shows the value used. (The Geospatial block country field is an example).

Dataverse also allows un-verified entry of metadata from external controlled vocabularies. In these cases, a compound field is often used so that the user can specify the name/URI of the vocabulary used. Examples include the keyword and topic fields which include subfields for the vocabulary URI and name, and the term (value in the vocabulary) chosen (without a field for a URL of the value itself). Other fields work similarly, e.g. the “Author” field which includes a subfield to select an identifier type (from an internally controlled list, that works as discussed above) and a separate text subfield to add a value (nominally an identifier from the identifier scheme/type selected, eg. ORCID).

For display of compound fields, Dataverse supports providing some HTML formatting of the parent and subfields. This allows creating links, concatenating subfield values into a single line on the page, etc. One potential limitation of this mechanism is that fields cannot reference each other, limiting the complexity of HTML that can be created)

Consensus Proposal

- The Dataverse software will provide administrators with the ability to link specific metadata fields to an externally maintained source of allowed values for that field.
- Users will be able to select values via an interface that allows selection from a drop down list, a list filtered based on what the user types, or other method appropriate to the type of metadata involved.
- The selected value will be displayed in Dataverse with information that supports user understanding of the term, i.e. rather than a raw URL, the display would show the term name, a short description that pops-up, and a link to an externally managed page that provides more information about the value. The display may be specific to the vocabulary involved and/or the source from which the information is obtained.
- Internally, the Dataverse software will manage such values with minimal duplication, i.e. by just storing the unique term URL with the Dataset version and keeping a separate table to capture additional information about the term (i.e. as a json blob). This means that fields in metablocks intended for use with external controlled vocabulary services would consist of a single field for the term URI rather than having a parent field with multiple child fields.
- The default in metadata exports will be to include just the term URI as the field value, although individual metadata exports will be able to access the internal table to discover/add additional metadata about that term as appropriate for the export format.
- The mechanism for associating a vocabulary(ies) and service with a given metadata field will involve specification of the service URL and the address of a Javascript file that will provide the UI for selecting a value and for displaying a value once it is saved. (The existing Dataverse mechanism for saving a field value will be invoked to transfer the value from the user's browser to the Dataverse server.)

Benefits

- The proposal is well aligned with the existing work by DANS to provide support via SKOSMOS services while simplifying the internal representation of controlled values (and then potentially simplifying the functionality required in a service's associated Javascript file, as well as making it Dataverse-independent).
- Any vocabulary that can be managed via a SKOSMOS server would be immediately supported.
- The mechanism is easily extensible to other types of services such that would support ORCID, FundRef, ROR, sample PIDs, etc.

- Would support internationalization (i18n) for any services that provide i18n support
- The general mechanism (storing a term URI only, having a table to cache additional info about the term URI) should be extensible w.r.t using CVV in variable-level metadata, etc. (perhaps for licenses as well?) while avoiding any need to mimic the parent/child field structure of metadata blocks.

Limitations

- Potentially allows stylistic differences between Dataverse and the input/display options supported in the service Javascripts
 - Rationale: The proposed design reduces the degree of coupling between Dataverse and various vocabulary sources. The potential for UI style differences can be mitigated via CSS rules. Further, there is also an argument that CVV fields should display in similar ways across applications, which is easier to manage with Javascripts that can potentially be shared across applications.
- Requires changes to existing fields such as the citation block's keyword field that have been configured with multiple children
 - Rationale: Since the keyword field doesn't yet have a termURI child field, any design would require some change from the current structure. The choices proposed would either add termURI as a 4th child field or replace the keyword parent/child structure with a single field. Given that there's a change regardless, a design that simplifies the keyword field and makes any existing or new custom field CVV-capable without adding a parent/child structure seems like the better approach. The best approach to upgrading current entries is still to be developed, but is likely to be vocabulary dependent.
- Local constraints on allowed values (within the values allowed in a vocabulary) are not supported
 - Rationale: While this is of interest within the community, this would add scope and would potentially complicate interoperability between instances (if they allow different subsets of the terms in a vocabulary). Given this, the choice is being made to treat this as a separate, future, issue.
- Possible lack of support for free-text and controlled values
 - Rationale: The underlying design choice would support free-text values as well as termURIs. However, since input is controlled by Javascripts, whether this is supported will depend on whether it is supported in the Javascript. That said, there are type-ahead Javascript widgets that allow saving the exact text typed regardless of whether a matching value from the CVV is found, so support could be relatively straight forward.
- No support for multiple vocabularies coming from different services (using different Javascripts)
 - Rationale: Hopefully, most multi-vocabulary use cases will involve vocabularies provided by one service (i.e. SKOSMOS). If multiple

vocabularies from different services (supported by different Javascripts) is needed, the design should be possible to extend.

- Internal table implies coupling of Dataverse to specific services
 - Rationale: Unless it is acceptable to have Dataverse only store the termURI, and only have that URI available to put in metadata exports, some coupling will be required. That said, the proposed design can hopefully minimize the coupling, i.e. by storing service/CVV-specific json information in the internal table. It may also be possible for most/all services to simply make an http request to the term URI requesting json content to populate the table (versus having service/CVV-specific logic in the core of Dataverse). It should also be noted that the design does minimize coupling w.r.t. input and display and the potential for coupling is primarily related to metadata exports.
- No existing market for Dataverse-agnostic Javascripts
 - Rationale: One of the arguments for using Javascripts to manage input and display (aside from reducing coupling) is that such Javascripts could be used across different applications and could potentially be maintained with help from efforts beyond Dataverse. This may be the case for the SKOSMOS Javascript already. For other Javascripts, it is likely that the Dataverse community will need to help advocate for the use of shared Javascripts if we wish to share maintenance costs.
- Internal CVV fields are still managed differently.
 - Rationale: Yes, Dataverse has a mechanism to store the values allowed in a controlled vocabulary defined as a list in a metadata block. This mechanism isn't sufficient to handle use cases such as keywords or the other types of services for external CVVs. However, it is likely that the new mechanism in this proposal could support internal CVVs as well and thus, as a future improvement, unify how internal and external CVVs are handled.

Required Development

This proposal leverages the work already done in PR [#7712](#). The additional work needed to implement the proposal above includes:

1. Creation of a new vocabulary table (termUri string, term metadata (json text))
 - Column for service type/URL?
 - Column for retrieval date?
2. Add CRUD API for vocabulary table. API would allow addition of a termURI and would then perform a web call to populate the term metadata (versus allowing user input of metadata)
3. Adapt current PR to add termURI to table during upload.
4. Adapt current PR (config file example) to work with a single field versus parent/4 child model
5. Adapt SKOSMOS Javascript to handle display as well as input.

6. Develop plan for migrating existing keyword entries to new model
 - E.g. identify existing CVV entries and identify/create SKOSMOS service to provide them, develop sql script to replace existing values
7. Develop recommendations/documentation/examples to support using CVVs in keyword and custom fields.
8. Optional: Support free-text or CVV from SKOSMOS
9. Optional: update Javascript to display i18n value matching the current UI setting for locale/language
10. Optional: Consider Javascript caching options for SKOSMOS, e.g. mirroring the use of local browser storage in the ORCID script
11. Optional: Test/adapt ORCID script to work with PR's config mechanism
12. Optional: Consider any other Javascript dev in parallel (FundRef, ROR, etc.)
13. Optional: Adapt ORE export and any others to write out more than just the term URI

Controlled Vocabulary Value Support Frequently Asked Questions List

- 1. What will I need to do to set this up, i.e. if I want to use a subject vocabulary as a choice for keywords?*
 - For the keywords field in particular, the first step will be to inspect existing values and decide how to handle them (see Question 2)
 - For the keyword, or any other field, if the vocabulary you want to use is available from an existing SKOSMOS server (see [list](#)), you'll just need to use a new API to register that vocabulary, from that server, for that specific field.
 - That's it. If you want to use a vocabulary not in SKOSMOS, see question 3.
- 2. Our Dataverse instance uses a CVV for keywords already (e.g. the [ICPSR Thesaurus](#)). What will I need to do to upgrade to the Dataverse release that includes the new CVV support?*
 - The basic change required for any existing keywords is to replace the combination of term, vocabulary URI, and vocabulary name currently stored in the three keyword child fields with the corresponding term URI. We anticipate scripts that can help automate this process, but a mapping from the existing values to a termURI will still be needed. (There are some short-term options, such as simply concatenating the existing values into one value that could be a work-around). Once the existing values are mapped to a single field form, you will be able to use other vocabularies as discussed in question 1.
 - For any vocabulary that is available in machine-readable format (e.g. for ICPSR there appears to be a [TemaTres service](#)), a Javascript could be developed to provide formatted display, or, if desired, to also allow selection for new entries. An alternative would be to inject the vocabulary into a SKOSMOS service (see question 3).
- 3. I want to use a vocabulary that no one else in the community is using yet. What do I have to do?*

There are two primary options:

 - For static vocabularies, one option would be to use an existing or new SKOSMOS service and to register the vocabulary with it. Documentation exists on how to do this. If this is a common issue for the community, running a SKOSMOS server could potentially be a feature offered by GDCC and/or specific community members. Once the vocabulary is available, the registration process described in question 1 is all that is needed.
 - For dynamic vocabularies (i.e. comprised of PIDs for people, samples, organizations, etc.), one would instead develop a Javascript that would use the underlying service's API to retrieve lists of possible entries for input and to retrieve metadata to generate the display for chosen values. This approach could also be used for any other non-SKOSMOS services. Once a Javascript exists, it can be registered as described in question 1.
- 4. The support for internal CVVs, done by adding a list in a metadata block seems so*

simple by comparison. Why is the proposed support for externally managed vocabularies so complex/ has involved so much discussion?

While the core concern in both cases is to allow selection from a defined list of values, which may have i18n translations, there are several differences in these use cases and/or in the level of functionality involved:

- Externally managed terms have more metadata, i.e. an association with a vocabulary name/URI, a description/definition, relationships to other terms, etc., many of which can also have i18n translations. The Dataverse software's internal CVV mechanism doesn't support displaying any such information - either during term selection or for a chosen term.
- Many external vocabularies are large enough that a simple list of all values, or even sending all possible values to your browser at once is not practical.
- There is no single standard for how vocabularies are served (though SKOSMOS is being used for many relevant to our community)
- There is no single source/no single service from which all vocabularies can be retrieved.

While these differences do require some additional sophistication, the discussion has led to a design that keeps the internal changes to Dataverse fairly simple and vocabulary/service agnostic, with most of the logic for input and display managed in Javascripts that can be maintained separately.

5. *What happens if a vocabulary service goes away or I decide to not configure a field to use that vocabulary any more?*

The proposed design stores the termURI as the value for the field. If the service is temporarily unavailable, or you decide not to use it any longer, the field would just show the raw termURI string, and users could still add termURIs by cut/paste in that field in new datasets. Although not part of the proposal currently, since the design contains a table caching the metadata about a termURI (such as the term name and the name of the vocabulary it comes from), it will be possible to add support to provide a more user friendly display (e.g. the term name in the UI's current language as an HTTP link to the termURI) when the service is no longer configured and potentially as a backup if the external CVV service is down. Similarly, if the intent is to not allow further use of a vocabulary but to keep existing instances where it was used, future extensions to the proposed design should be able to provide display formatting while not listing that vocabulary as an input option.

6. *ORCIDs and other PIDs seem like a different use case. Why are they being considered here?*

Being able to query <https://orcid.org> to select Authors of a Dataset was originally raised in this working group discussion primarily as a way to demonstrate how the Dataverse software could store only a termURI (the URL form of the person's ORCID in this case) and have Javascript provide both input and display mechanisms, versus using multiple child fields as with the current Author metadata field and the keyword field. Using one

field and relying on Javascript to format the input and display has advantages - one doesn't have to validate that the term name in one child field is consistent with the term URI selected in another, i18n can be handled more easily, display can be managed without requiring parsing the parent/child structure that is specific to Dataverse, new custom fields don't have to be designed with parent/child structure, etc. - that are independent of whether one only wants to support CVVs or also support other PIDs.

One additional advantage of the proposed design is that it localizes the logic required to handle the differences between CVVs and PIDs into service-specific Javascripts that all interact with Dataverse in the same way. This means, that with the addition of associating a specific Javascript with the individual vocabularies/PIDs as part of configuration, there is no additional work required to make the design 'PID-ready'.

Supporting a specific PID system then becomes a matter of finding/creating an appropriate Javascript - something that can be done in parallel or in follow-on work. At a minimum, we expect that the ORCID support demonstrated in the working group (based on Javascript originally developed in the [SEAD project](#)) can be quickly modified to adapt to the final proposed design and enable use of ORCIDs in Author, Contact, and similar fields. The SKOSMOS script and this one can then serve as examples for supporting additional services.

Earlier Discussion

Requirements/Desired Functionality:

- Enable both metadata fields and variables in files to be associated with external vocabularies, e.g. from hosted services and/or static lists of values (json?, json-ld?, rdf?, xml?)
- Enable association with 'dynamic vocabularies', e.g. ORCID and other services providing identifiers for people, places, organizations, papers, ...
 - and/or to validate manually entered values (e.g. to confirm a DOI entered exists)
- Enable Dataverse to store the URI for vocabulary values
- Support auto-complete for internal/external CVVs
- Allow fields to be associated with multiple vocabularies and/or support controlled and free-text values (e.g. for keywords)
- Allow retrieval (and storage/display) of metadata about vocabulary values (e.g. the name/email of a person from their ORCID, having both the URI and label, and perhaps explanatory text for a Keyword or Topic/Subject entry)
 - and/or validate that manually entered values (such as name/email for an Author) match the analogous metadata associated with a provided ORCID)
- Gracefully handle situations where an external vocabulary is temporarily or permanently off-line
- Allow Admins to constrain the vocabulary values allowed (e.g. to limit the set of Topics/Subjects supported in a Dataverse by specifying a subject of topics from an external vocabulary that can be entered)
- Change the display to allow linking out to an external page for a given term (e.g. to go to an Author's ORCID page, or to more information about a term such as [academic achievement](#))
- Simplify/consolidate display of the vocab/vocab URI/term/term URI/any metadata, e.g. showing a term label (or the name associated with an ORCID) as an html link to the term URI, with a hover-over display of the term's definition (or ORCID email if public), etc. (versus the current display usually defaulting to formatted but ~sequential display of subfields.)
- Support internationalization (i18n): displaying terms in the Dataverse instance's default locale and/or the user's preferred locale.
- Handle evolution, e.g. new versions of external vocabularies and/or updates to metadata (e.g. the wording of a definition of a given term or the email associated with an ORCID, the addition of new i18n language translations) in some fashion (TBD: questions such as should info associated with published versions be updated? Should changes be flagged (e.g. if an email for an ORCID will be updated in a draft datasetversion).

- Support hierarchical and/or graph-based ‘vocabularies’, e.g. vocabularies where terms are in categories and subcategories and/or where terms may have related terms (broader, narrower, similar, ...)
- Support controlled vocabularies in metadata fields that are not in metadata blocks, e.g. licenses and other TermsOfUseAndAccess, guestbook choices.
- Support download of CVV values in metadata export format(s) with sufficient info (such as the id/URI) to associate them with an externally defined controlled vocabulary.
- Support migration of existing fields/values to any new CVV capability
- Support use of CVVs as query terms, e.g. in advanced search, or adding a link/button to find datasets with the same CVV near the term itself in metadata displays.
- CVV entry via API

Discussion/Considerations:

Vocabulary sources:

- Dataverse’s metablocks support controlled vocabularies to some extent. A key missing feature is having an associated term URI. It would be simple to add one to the block definition, but this doesn’t, by itself, resolve the issue of how to manage store vocab values that have, at least, an id/URI and label
- A minimal model for CVVs is a label and id(e.g. URI). There are models with more information (e.g. ORCID, vocabularies that have definitions, etc.)
- RDF/Linked-Data centric CVVs should have URIs for terms, but vocabularies defined in XML, for example, may not.
- Vocabularies may/may not support i18n and/or particular languages. The language preferred by the submitter may/may not match the default locale or the retrievers’ preferences
- Service endpoints, e.g. skosmos, and static sources, e.g. posted RDF files are fairly similar with the exception that services can filter responses (e.g. for i18n, autocomplete). There are probably fewer service/protocol standards than there are variants of static sources, and service/protocols often can import static sources, so it may be simplest for Dataverse to only support service/protocol options. (That said, an option to point at a static json source with label/id fields might simplify the creation of simple CVVs compared to supporting them through metadata blocks directly.)
- Dataverse’s current design with support for CVVs using a compound field presents some issues:
 - Validation, e.g. checking that the vocabulary identified by URI actually has the label shown and allows the value listed becomes a cross-sub-field check. While it isn’t too hard to think how this can be done, e.g. setting a CVV updates the vocab URI/label, changing the URI clears the CVV field, etc. it is probably somewhat confusing to present these as independent choices in the UI. Alternatives might include a custom widget.

- I18n: while there will be one ID/URI per CVV, there may be more than one label (per locale). Having label as a separate field with a simple text value doesn't match this model well.
- Variance: to support anything beyond a label/id, e.g. additional metadata fields that would nominally be specific to a given vocabulary would require additional subfields, making the field structure vocabulary specific and potentially making it hard to have fields like keywords when vocabularies have different fields (minimally one might have extra empty fields if only one of several vocabularies has it)
- Temporal variance: While it's probably reasonable to assume/require external vocabs to create new versions if/when changes are made to which terms are included, and probably to require that URIs distinguish which version a term belongs to, Dataverse can't assume that metadata is constant per version (e.g. an email associated with an ORCID is expected to change, will vocab managers version when new languages are supported or definition text is slightly tweaked?)
- Display: While Dataverse's current markup language allows useful HTML formatting of compound fields, a language to allow more complex formatting across multiple fields, particularly for cases where multiple vocabularies are allowed in one field, and/or where compound fields don't represent controlled vocabulary information, may be more difficult than an alternative, in which, for example, formatting is handled in javascript, or formatting of a single (json) value filed based on an associated vocab URI field, might simplify things.
- Non-block metadata: TermsOfUseAndAccess fields are not datasetFields and so can't be compound.

It might be simpler to consider refactoring to only store/rely on ID/URIs and to either dynamically retrieve and/or cache metadata including labels/i18n labels. A design in which the vocabulary URI and term URI field types are also associated by more than being siblings beneath a parent field might also simplify setting up input and display.

- Validation/Legacy Data/APIs - with the current metadata structure (containing subfields), it will be possible for existing entries, and potentially new entries submitted via API to include combinations that are incorrect, e.g. an ORCID with the wrong name, or a term label with the wrong URI, etc. Changes at the source could also result in this, e.g. the description of a field is updated at the source. This suggests that Dataverse will either need a way to validate entries internally and/or to always treat everything but the term itself (e.g. the term URI) as cached information that could/should be revalidated.
- Mixed fields - supporting more than one vocabulary for a field, or a combination of vocabulary and free text also raises potential issues: different vocabularies may have different subfields (e.g. does a vocabulary URI exist) and free text would nominally not have any. Structuring the input/storage/display around a specific set of child fields is potentially cumbersome and may also lead to validation concerns (e.g. is a vocab URI being sent with a free text value via API?)

Current Options/Analysis:

nominally ~PR:

Basics: uses a setting to associate fields with vocabularies, adding a table to store the setting value in parsed form. The metadata edit form is annotated with information sufficient to allow javascript to manage the input, e.g. to display which vocabularies are allowed in one subfield and to provide auto-complete selection of terms in another.

Pros:

- Relatively simple design leveraging existing Dataverse metadata structure. The storage/display of metadata is exactly the same as if a user had manually filled in the same fields in the existing UI.
- Only skosmos is supported but this is a fairly flexible protocol.
-

Cons/current limitations:

- Validation - changing the vocabulary doesn't currently invalidate a term from another vocab list / keep subfields in sync
- Javascript is using english language as default - however overall support for i18n is supported by skosmos and currently implemented dependent on the language switch available in multi-lingual installations
- Uses the vocab URI field as the term URI / another field needed
- Doesn't address display changes

[PR #6521](#)

Basics: modifies the existing metadatablock definitions to allow terms to specify their display format to be associated with specific CVV/term values and adds the ability to manage formats, using the existing makeup language, associated with those CVV/terms. These capabilities are leveraged in the UI to allow, for example, a terms to be shown as a URI leveraging the label from one field and a URI from another.

Pros:

Cons:

[Orcidsupport](#) branch

Basics: Demonstrates use of a remote service (in this case ORCID via their public API) to allow add/edit and display of a field with metadata where Dataverse only stores the PID/URI for the identifier/term used. Similar to the Skosmos ~PR above, and could be adapted for use with Skosmos services, but postulates changing what is stored for a given field rather than having the service understand and populate the children of a compound field in Dataverse. Like #6521, it addresses display, using javascript rather than extending the display language in citation blocks.

Pros:

- Javascript is ~Dataverse independent - it looks for HTML elements marked as containing an ORCID (e.g. by having class='person') and extends them with multiple elements, and, analogously, looks for form input elements marked as associated with a person. This might make maintenance a sharable task.

- Can make identifying relevant HTML elements configurable (e.g. anything that can be used as a jquery selector) and can support CSS styling of the results.
- Simplifies - Dataverse doesn't need to manage compound fields that duplicate info from the remote service.
- ~single mechanism to handle input and display

Cons:

- Requires replacing compound fields
- Would not handle adding metadata (e.g. the name/email associated with an ORCID) to exported metadata without additional work. (Could generically cache json from remote services, or call the services as part of export.)

Design(s)

Combinations/extensions of the above and/or new ideas that will coherently support a useful fraction of the above requirements/desired features, hopefully in a manner that allows incremental development. Nominally a proposal should address at least 3 things:

- Mechanism to retrieve choices and enable user entry
- Mechanism to display values with associated metadata/child fields
- Changes to Dataverse metadata structure/storage to support these capabilities

How proposals meet/don't meet requirements should be addressed in the description and/or in the Requirements Matrix below.

1. [PR #7712](#)

- Uses [SKOSMOS server](#) as a source of vocabulary terms and metadata (e.g. name, description, vocab URI associated with a term URI). [SKOSMOS API specification](#) also implemented as a common interface by [CESSDA Controlled Vocabulary Service](#) that could be considered as another important source to connect to Dataverse.
- Adds an API to associate a vocabulary(ies) with a given parent field, which must have 4 child fields for term URL, term name, vocab name, and vocab URL. (Would initially apply to a modified keyword field and/or custom fields defined in other metadata blocks)
- Uses Javascript to manage term selection and populates the 4 child fields appropriately. Does not change the display for saved metadata.

2. Simplified CVV Fields

- Basic concept: support use of external services such as SKOSMOS to support term selection but simplify Dataverse's internal management of CVV entries by making them a single field for the term URL instead of having a parent with multiple children.
- Admin specifies vocab(s) associated with a given field name/RDF URI in the CVV configuration file.
- Dataverse metadata pages add an attribute(s) to the input/display field for that term that indicate the vocab(s) supported

- Multi-lingual support of CVV entries implemented based on the language switch in the interface. However admin can also specify default language in the [configuration file](#) (see configuration settings).
- Javascript(s) supporting those vocabs manage input and display of those fields, e.g.
 - Input via a type-ahead/dropdown menu widget. Interface shows either one input or for multiple vocabs, just a vocab selector and an input field.
 - Display leverages html to, for example, show the term name as a link to the term URL, with a hover-over pop-up showing a description/additional info. (label<a/>) Format could be different for different types of vocabs/managed by relevant javascript
- Initial implementation could rely on Javascript to dynamically retrieve term metadata (name, description, vocab name/URL, etc.) from service, but design could also add a CVV table that maps a termURI to a json object (blob) with the service response cached (so one entry per term, not storing all metadata per Dataset)
 - Per Dataset, we store only the TermURI
 - New table that stores, for a TermURI key, the label (and i18n versions) and description(i18n)
 - Could have an API (timer?) to refresh TermURI table (one entry or all, or all matching a pattern, etc.)
- Could co-exist with current capabilities, e.g. this capability would be added and we would convert some fields (keyword, creator?, contact?) but the ability to have a parent with subfields would still exist and could be used elsewhere.

Variants:

- Proposal 1 but use a single field to start? (new fields could be set up this way - keywords as is either wouldn't be set up or would only use the term URL field?) - i.e. if we want ~both proposals above, this is a potential step to align them earlier.

Requirements Matrix

(which proposals address which requirements)

Design (column) versus requirement (rows)	#7712	Simplified CVV Fields
Applies to any field?	Would support keyword field (with addition of one child field) and any	Would be stored as a single text field (holding the term URL) so could

	new/existing fields built to have the 4 required child fields.	potentially be applied to existing text fields without modifying the metadata block, e.g. subject, funder id, etc. (assuming Javascripts to handle those are available. Presumably we start with just a SKOSMOS Javascript) For keywords, would have to restructure to be a single field with no children.
Supports any vocab?	Currently specific to SKOSMOS which handles many vocabs. Could be extended.	~Assumes Javascript(s) know the authoritative source for each vocab. Can leverage SKOSMOS for many but others would require new Javascript (no further changes to Dataverse though).
Supports any type of (compound) value?	Assumes 4 specific subfields per value (term name/URL, vocab name/URL)	Requires a simple text field, no children. Accommodates different metadata about term / how to display it is handled by service/vocab-specific Javascript
Provides a clean input experience?	Display retains the 4 fields even though one selection determines all 4. Could hide/disable other fields (has this been done?)	Javascript controls display which can be specific to the type of data. For SKOSMOS-served vocabs, Javascript overrides the single entry field.
Provides clean display?	Doesn't change display so term appears as 4 child fields (up from 3)	Javascript manages display and would, for SKOSMOS for example, display the

	arranged by Dataverse.	term name as a clickable link that is the term URL, so display would not show long URLs by default.
Allows configuration of display?	Doesn't add to Dataverse's current metadatablock capabilities to format individual child fields. Could adopt #6521 as well to allow formatting across child fields.	Managed by Javascript, which could be customized (not ideal). Assuming a CVV tabled with cached Json/JsonLD, generic json-formatted output could be implemented and or a variant of #6521 could allow generating html from the json value.
Easy to administer?	Admins use an API to assign vocabs (and associated service URL? And javascript to use.) with a given field.	~Same
Interoperable across DV instances?	Would require same/superset CVV config to import data/metadata from another instance. If not configured, shows as 4 child fields.	~Same. If not configured, terms from unsupported vocabs would just show as their URLs.
Avoids incorrect entries (internally inconsistent, or different datasets having different info about the same URL)?	Javascript fills in 4 fields - could (does it already?) disable other inputs or validate to make sure term name matches term URL, etc. Would have to manage API as well (though presumably inconsistent entry via API would be rare). Information is replicated with every	Only one entry. CVV Table would have one copy of the mapping between term URL and metadata (name, vocab name, URL). API would just accept term URL (simpler) but neither design currently checks that an API submission is from an allowed vocab. (Both probably could). Changes at

	Dataset, so if the results from SKOSMOS change, different Datasets may have different values. (Should also be rare - bad practice to make changes to a vocab without versioning.)	the service would be ignored/could globally refresh the CVV table value, so all Datasets would have the same info.)
i18n?	Not supported. Could potentially be added by Javascript retrieving correct language value dynamically (or caching in a CVV table as in the other design)	CVV table could hold one copy if i18n entries that could be displayed. (Could have Dataverse put value in correct language hidden on the page for Javascript to use or Javascript could query DV for the right value via API)
Gracefully handles service outage (short term/intermittent)? Gracefully handles service outage (long-term/end-of-life)?	Reverts to just showing 4 child fields?	With CVV Table, can always show values for saved metadata. Input reverts to just showing one text field that can accept term URI.
Gracefully handle service moves/config to use different services? Authoritative services?	Since the service URL is part of config, can configure to use other services (a locally managed one, a mirror, etc.) Admin is responsible for using an authoritative source.	Assumes the Javascript knows the service URL/availability of mirrors, etc.)
Ready to go?	PR created If the only standard metadata field changed is the keyword field (needs the 4th child field), this PR would be limited to	Could leverage other PR but would require modification. Main new requirement would be for a CVV table and it's CRUD capabilities.

	keywords and new custom fields. That could potentially be a good thing if this is an intermediate step towards the other design (only keywords would have to be updated for most installations, but installations that require other fields can add them now.)	
Backward Compatible?	Adds a 4th child to keyword, flyway script needed to adapt existing entries if 4th field can't be null.	Would remove child fields from keyword, so (more complex) flyway script needed to remove other fields and populate a CVV table.
Can mix non-managed CVV or free-text values in same field?	Existing display is OK, input could allow disabling the selector with some 'manual' mode.	Using a combo widget that lets you start typing text and shows matching selection options, you can allow entry of that text (i.e. you type a URL and even if it doesn't match any entry, you can allow it to be stored as text). However, without some work (e.g. manual entries added to the CVV table, only the term URL can be displayed.)
Applicability to other CVV uses?	Both designs can leverage SKOSMOS as middleware - as long as a vocab can be added to a SKOSMOS server, the same Javascript/Dataverse modifications will support it.	In addition, creating a CVV table could be generally useful if CVV terms are to be used in DDI variable level metadata. Could also be useful to cache license info (the Multilicense proposal includes a license

		<p>table that is basically a cache of license metadata (name, short description, icon) for a license URL.</p> <p>Not assuming 4 subfields would also allow this to support things like ORCID's where first name, last name, email need to be cached - similar for grants, funder ids ,RARs, etc.</p> <p>A CVV table could also support local CVVs, e.g. as we have now in the metadata blocks for language and country. A site admin could add terms to the table to support a new vocab without an external service.</p>
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SKOSMOS deployments

The list of SKOSMOS instances with ready to use controlled vocabularies:

- Finto (Finland) <http://finto.fi>
- DANS-KNAW (Netherlands) SKOSMOS (in progress)
- BARTOC <http://bartoc-skosmos.unibas.ch/en/>
- CESSDA ELSST (European Language Social Science Thesaurus) <https://thesauri.cessda.eu/elsst/en/>
- ACDH Vocabularies (DARIAH, Austrian Academy of Sciences) <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/en/>
- Thesaurus INRAE (France) <https://vocabulary.irstea.fr/skosmos/>
- AGROVOC Multilingual Thesaurus (United Nations) <http://www.fao.org/agrovoc/>
- UNESCO Thesaurus <http://vocabularies.unesco.org>
- European Space Agency ESA NDE <https://fedeo.spacebel.be/thesaurus/en/>
- Loterre (France) <https://www.loterre.fr/skosmos/fr/>
- TIB (Germany) <https://labs.tib.eu/skosmos/en/>
- ScoLOMFR <https://www.reseau-canope.fr/scolomfr/data/scolomfr-6-0/>
- OZCAR-Theia (France) <https://in-situ.theia-land.fr/skosmos/>

- Direção-Geral do Livro, dos Arquivos e das Bibliotecas (Portugal) <http://skosmos.dglab.gov.pt/skosmos/en/>
- Salonmanga (Spain) <http://salonmanga.rtve.es/skosmos/>
- Silknow (Spain) <https://skosmos.silknow.org/thesaurus/>
- GDI-RIP (Germany) <https://www.geoportal.rlp.de/skosmos/en/>
- Université de Paris (France) <https://gravi165.step.univ-paris-diderot.fr/vocabularies/en/>
- INED (France) thesaurus.web.ined.fr/navigateur/en/